

Beyond the Insult: My Journey and Fascination with Invective

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I wrote this article, past the celebration of the World Teachers Day which was yesterday (October 5, 2025), and it also concurred with the public presentation of my recently completed study that dealt on a linguistic phenomenon called “invective”. I recently presented my paper entitled “*Use of Invective in Online Verbal Aggression Among Filipino Social Media Expressive Contributors Engaged in Affective Political Discourse*” (Unciano, 2025) in a virtual gathering of educators, academicians, scholars, and researchers. My latest research presentation actually features my extension study of a previous study that I wrote on the same topic. I also presented my earlier invective-inspired research in two international conferences last September 2025, wherein my study bagged several major awards of “best in research abstract”, “best full research paper”, and “best in paper presentation”. My noble purpose was mainly to have the broadest possible dissemination of my research, and those events where I presented my paper was attended by almost a hundred different educational and academic institutions and universities based in the Philippines and other countries. I have been joining national and international research conferences since 2014, and I have always regarded it as an honor to be welcomed in the midst of prestigious academic circles serving as an audience to listen to the merits of my research findings.

As I mentioned in my earlier public presentations that I found the impetus to develop this study because I, myself, am an avid user of Facebook. It's amazing that I have been using FB for the past “16 years”, since I created my FB account in August 2009. Hence, it's a sort of an anniversary tribute when I started working on my study about the use of invective by social media users last August. I want to think of it as a commemorative celebration of my almost two decades of using FB. However, that was not really intentional because what actually prompted me to work on this study is because of the explosion of scandals in political corruption involving flood control projects last August of this year. The “public outrage” among my fellow Filipinos began with multiple, simultaneous online posts, largely from regular citizens last August. The social media posts were amplified by journalists and government officials, bringing widespread attention to the issue. The scandal further gained momentum after posts featured the lavish lifestyles of individuals connected to construction firms involved in questionable government projects. It was last

August when Philippine President Marcos revealed initial audit findings that identified contractors who collectively received billions of pesos in flood control contracts. In that same month, he personally inspected substandard anti-flood structures and confirmed a P77 million "ghost project".

As a daily user of Facebook where I usually draw opportunities for entertainment and relaxation, I started encountering random aggressive posts that appear on my newsfeed from media personalities, netizens, and even officials from the government giving their opinions and vulgar verbal reactions about the scandalous expose of corruption over the flood control projects. The volume of online posts and articles over the issue has ballooned as the days went by, occupying a large fraction or share of the topics tackled by FB users. Viewing these posts from my lens as a language scholar, I noticed varied ways that people expressed their outrage over the issue. That specific event of political corruption has turned into a subject of online verbal aggression, showcasing the peculiar ways that Filipino FB users expressed their anger. As I observed that the number of these posts started to build up in frequency everyday, I decided to capture some of these posts and analyzed them in terms of their inherent use of "invective". Eventually, I thought of formalizing my observations in a research. In a subsequent attempt to broaden my investigations, I created an extension study that also analyzed the telos or objective purpose of the Facebook posts. Since it was an interesting analysis, I also tried to generate a Filipino-sensitized descriptive language model where I described language patterns and regularities in the way Filipino users of FB express verbally their anger on social media, especially when they are stimulated to react on issues of political corruption, such as the current issues of corruption involving flood control projects.

Explaining it in layman's terms, low invective language is straightforward, crude, and blunt. It's the kind of insult you hear in everyday arguments and is intended to wound by being as direct as possible. It relies on simple, offensive words that get straight to the point. In contrast, high invective is creative, clever, and it often uses formal language to deliver a polished, sophisticated insult. It requires verbal skills in executing wit or sarcasm.

For the purpose of this article, I wish to dig deeper on the reasons I was personally inclined and curious about "invective", which was why I chose it as my research phenomenon. The incidental prevalence of online aggression on social media that became a rich mine of aggressive Facebook posts utilizing invective forms and strategies was a good formal justification that I actually indicated in my research study. But then, even long before such issues of political corruption exploded on social media, I was in fact linked to issues about the use of invective several years ago in my very own Facebook. This is what I want to talk about in this article. One way or another, we are urged express some verbal aggression using our social media account, although we all differ in ways of expressing our verbal aggression online. I recall the year 2016 when my Facebook newsfeed at that time was filled with lots of aggressive posts from employees, students and relatives of students that expressed and pungently criticized the corrupt and irregular practices in a state university. They were particularly addressed to the university's president

and members of his administration. There was a point when I participated in those dialogues that were openly staged online. After all, it has been a regular and normal social media practice for me over many years to render my own comments when I see interesting posts on newsfeed like social or political issues, gender, religious and moral issues that do not have to be connected at all in the university. For 18 years now of using Facebook, it comes natural to me that I share my insights and opinions. I still do that even to this day. After all, I am an academician, and a philosophy major with an orientation to be critical about issues and ideas I encounter. To me, it is an exercise of democratic expression or that I see it as a democratic and academic participation over certain dialogues on social topics, which I believe is an extension of academic freedom, especially that I find the issues worthy of academic deliberation.

However, in 2016, I noticed that some persons in the university (even among “officials” occupying high, respectable administrative designations), used unfavorable ways of expressing their disagreement to my ideas or opinions posted on my Facebook. While my posts dealt on issues and criticisms over university policies, as well as actions or decisions made by certain officials, some “allies” of the university president who disagreed with me, trying to defend him were laced with “ad hominem” attacks, low invective language, and gutter rhetoric. I really condemned these expressions of aggression against my posts and so I decided then to write an informal complaint letter to the university administration. With that letter, I attached those FB posts that contained graphic language and images and even libelous imputations against my person which were not even addressing directly those issues that I raised on social media. Well, I can be very pungent and sarcastic too when expressing indignation but then I try to keep a tone suited for an “eloquent fury” or a “poised indignation”. I expressed in my letter to the university president that the “gutter style” of his “allies” who targeted me in their FB posts were somehow intent to motivate me to higher levels of anger. I was also critical over the fact that they are highly educated people in the academe but surprisingly lack rhetoric style in expressing their aggression even on social media. My complaint then fell on deaf ears, since I also expected the university president to favor the behaviors of his own allies. In fact, they turned the complaint against me instead by imputing malice on my posts on Facebook.

Memories over that incident are somehow refreshed when I did my recent study about invective, reliving my rather unfavorable encounters of invective use on social media several years ago. I write this article to share some reflections about that experience. I learned that people turn to use low invective when they perceive themselves to be losing an argument or they want to divert from the issue because they have no argument to offer. So a person starts to attack the person they want to oppose rather than the substance of his / her argument. Insults in the form of low invective can be used as a defense mechanism to mask insecurity or a lack of valid counter-arguments. By lashing out, the person attempts to protect his ego and salvage his pride when logic fails. Moreover, when a person perceives that his / her status is threatened by losing an argument, he may resort to low invective

insults to diminish the other person's social standing and, by comparison, raise their own. This is exemplified by aggressive posts directed to me that spoke about my gender instead of targeting my arguments. As such, low invective insults actually act as a "red herring", which involves shifting attention away from the weakness of one's own argument towards the character of the other person. It forces the person you are opposing to defend himself, thereby distracting him from the original topic. I became a victim of persons who directed their aggression against me on social media and that they were inclined to use low invective. It was pretty much of a gutter experience to witness that from persons I least expect to use low invective since they also come from the university.

What my research on invective simply demonstrated is the frequency that people use either high or low invective but the research framework was not oriented to investigate the WHY. My social media encounters with some persons in the university in 2016 indicates that some people really prefer low over high invective, or that they may not be capable at all of executing a high invective language. And if I were to complement this gap in my research which failed to explain this aspect of the phenomenon of invective, I believe that the reasons behind preferences in using invective forms have to do with "cognitive limitations", "emotional regulation issues", and "lack of exposure to sophisticated language". The ability to use high invective requires a relatively broader vocabulary and a better command of rhetorical devices like metaphor, irony, etc. and the ability to construct complex, creative insults. Moreover, generating high invective is cognitively demanding because it requires creative thinking and rapid processing. Some people may not have the capacity for this kind of verbal agility and instead rely on more simplistic and readily accessible insults. Likewise, a person who is very angry or distressed or in high emotion may have a compromised ability to engage in complex thought and careful word selection, so that the quickest and most direct verbal attack is to use low invective, which offers an immediate emotional release. Using low invective such my encounters then of aggressive FB posts that targeted me harshly by means of "name-calling" is direct and visceral, delivering an insult with immediate and unambiguous force. These were meant to cause immediate emotional pain on me or they may be desiring to escalate the conflict by inducing stronger hatred in their victim.

In conclusion, I believe that learning to express anger in a refined, scholarly way is about channeling that emotion into a structured, logical critique, not just upgrading one's insults. Nevertheless, there may be a few benefits when you have the skill to execute high invective. It is a demonstration of one's rhetorical skill and wit. Unlike simple, crude insults, high invective showcases a mastery of language and a clever wit. It can also effectively criticize public figures. In fact, political satirists and comedians frequently use high invective to attack public figures by highlighting their flaws in a creative and pointed way to spark public discourse.